

Chlorosulphonation of Phthalide and Derivatives

R. D'COSTA and V. V. NADKARNY*

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, Chemistry Department, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-400001

Manuscript received 17 September 1974; accepted 13 January 1975

Chlorosulphonation of phthalide yielded 6-phthalide sulphonyl chloride and from it, a number of crystalline derivatives were synthesized.

THE perusal of the available literature shows that, while nitration of phthalide is studied,¹⁻³ chlorosulphonation of the molecule has not been attempted. Hence in the present investigation, chlorosulphonation of phthalide is discussed. No solvent was employed. From the chlorosulphonation experiments, it was observed that

- (i) phthalide sulphonic acid formed at 100°, was isolated as the sodium salt;
- (ii) 6-phthalide sulphonyl chloride at 130° with good yields.

The formation of phthalide sulphonyl chloride was confirmed by oxidizing the same to 4-sulphophthalic⁴ acid, a known compound listed in the literature.

The 6-phthalide sulphonyl chloride thus obtained, was condensed with ammonia, amines, phenols and a thiol to give derivatives having the following structure :

Experimental

1. Chlorosulphonation of Phthalide at 130°

To 1 g. of phthalide, added dropwise 4.5 ml. chlorosulphonic acid, the mixture swirled and refluxed in an oil bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture on pouring into ice-water, separated a colourless oil, which solidified on chilling. The solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. Colourless crystals melting

TABLE—CONDENSED PRODUCTS OF 6-PHTHALIDE SULPHONYL CHLORIDE

	Mol. formula	M.P.	Yield %	Calc. %		Found %	
				N	S	N	S
(a) Ammonia	C ₈ H ₇ O ₄ SN	151°-2°	70	6.57	15.02	6.48	14.91
(b) Aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ SN	147°-8°	68	4.84	11.07	4.71	10.98
(a) Benzylamine	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ SN	98°-9°	68	4.62	10.56	4.55	10.49
(b) <i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ SNCl	187°-8°	65	4.32	9.89	4.25	9.75
(a) <i>p</i> -Anisidine	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₅ SN	91°	70	4.38	10.03	4.26	9.91
(a) Phenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ S	90°-1°	45	—	11.03	—	10.97
(c) 2-Naphthol	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₅ S	83°-4°	40	—	9.46	—	9.38
(a) Thiosalicylic Acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆ S ₂	300°-1°	60	—	9.14	—	9.08

(a) = colourless, (b) = yellow-Orange yellow, (c) = light pink.

at 101°–102°. Yield, 49%. Found : S, 13.68; Cl, 15.15. $C_8H_5O_4S$ Cl requires : C, 13.76; Cl, 15.26%.

2. *Reaction of Phthalide Sulphonyl Chloride with Ammonia*

To 0.5 g. of phthalide sulphonyl chloride dissolved in benzene, dry ammonia gas was bubbled for a period of 10 min. A colourless solid, which, when crystallised from alcohol-water mixture, yielded long needles.

3. *Reactions of Phthalide Sulphonyl Chloride with Amines*

To 1 g. phthalide sulphonyl chloride dissolved in pyridine, added 0.45 g. of the appropriate amine in pyridine. The mixture refluxed on a water bath for an hour, cooled, poured into cold excess 2*N* hydrochloric acid. The precipitate of *N*-substituted sulphonamide was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol water or acetone-water mixture.

4. *Reactions of Phthalide Sulphonyl Chloride with Phenols*

To 1 g. of phthalide sulphonyl chloride in pyridine, added 0.45 g. of the corresponding phenol in pyridine. The mixture, refluxed on a water bath for an hour, cooled, poured into cold excess 2*N* hydrochloric acid. The solution decanted and the product extracted with ether. The ether layer treated with 5 per cent solution of sodium hydroxide, washed with cold water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and finally evaporated. The residue was crystallised from alcohol-water mixture.

References'

1. KURBATOW, *Ann.*, 1880, 202, 219.
2. T. TEPPEME, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1923, 42, 30.
3. J. TIROUFLET, (*Faculte. Sci. Rennes. France*), *Bull. Soc. Sci.*, Bretagne Special No. 26, 1951, 7–122.
4. *Chem. News*, 1922, 125, 320; *Chem. Abs.*, 1923, 17, 742.